

A study of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Qualification, Age, Marital Status and Parents' Occupation

Dr. Bhagwan Balani,

Assistant Professor,

Bombay Teachers' Training College, Colaba, Mumbai

Introduction

“Teaching creates all other professions.”

~Author Unknown

Teaching is the specialized application of knowledge, skills and attributes designed to provide unique service to meet the educational needs of the individual and of society. The choice of learning activities whereby the goals of education are realized in the school is the responsibility of the teaching profession. A more viable starting point in education could be to perceive entrepreneurial education as a means to achieve more interest, joy, engagement and creativity among students (Johannisson, 2010, Lackéus, 2013). “The secret of getting ahead is getting started.” ~*Mark Twain, Write*. The rapid development of IT technology also provides many opportunities for learning entrepreneurship skills (Zunfeng and Chunling, 2011), or for college students to start their own businesses (Chen et al., 2012). The academicians of all the disciplines are in search of finding out the pedagogical skills to empower their students with entrepreneurial skills so that they can sustain themselves in the growing competitive world. Teacher education institutions across the world are in the process revamping their programmes so that they can meet the future challenges of the growing educational industry. There is lot of pressure on the Ministry of Human Resource Department in India to revamp the teacher education in India. The NCTE is also working day and night to enhance the quality of school education and teacher education in India.

Literature Review

(Beránek, 2015), Studied Attitude of the College Students to Entrepreneurial Skills Development in the Subject E-Commerce. The outcomes of the study clearly indicated that entrepreneurship skills are being developed except for a motivation of students to accept a risky business competitive environment. However, the propensity to take risk is one of the

basic traits of successful entrepreneurs. Our future effort will aim therefore at modifying our educational content. Greater emphasis will be placed on how to teach students to accept competitive environment which is risky and mostly unpredictable.

(Chaudhary, 2017), analysed the demographic Factors, Personality and Entrepreneurial Inclination among 274 students from two new and upcoming universities in an emerging economy of India. The outcome of the study revealed that the traits of locus of control, tolerance for ambiguity, self-confidence and innovativeness were significant in differentiating entrepreneurs from non-entrepreneurs. The need for achievement and risk-taking propensity were not found to be significantly different for these two groups which was contradictory to the expectations. The study revealed that the role of family background and school also plays a significant role in predicting entrepreneurial inclination among students. In her concluding remarks the researcher noted that public policy implications for education system in India which largely prepares the students for jobs in public and private sectors rather than entrepreneurship.

(Pouratashi, 2015), studied the levels and determinants of entrepreneurial intentions amongst agricultural students of Tehran. The findings revealed that about a half of the respondents had medium entrepreneurial intentions. The researcher observed significant differences in entrepreneurial intentions between students who had attended entrepreneurship courses and those who had not. Also, there were differences in entrepreneurial intentions between students who had self-employed parents and those who had not.

(Wang, Chang, Yao, & Liang, August 2016), studied Contribution of Self-Efficacy to the Relationship between Personality Traits and Entrepreneurial Intention. The outcomes of the study revealed that entrepreneurial intention comprised two dimensions: conviction and preparation. Accordingly, the mediation model of self-efficacy was partially supported. Extraversion, openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness reliably predict both conviction and preparation, whereas neuroticism did not. In addition to the indirect effects, both openness and negative emotion exert a direct effect on entrepreneurial intention in agricultural students.

(Culbertson, Smith, & Leiva, May 2011), studied the role of Goal Orientation and Self-Efficacy to enhance entrepreneurship among 158 college students. Research suggested that motivational traits are important in pursuing entrepreneurial activities. The researcher further noted that the extent to which factors influencing entrepreneurial versus managerial goals differ remains unclear. This study assessed the influence of goal orientation and self-efficacy in predicting entrepreneurial and managerial career anchors development. The study also indicated learning goal orientation (LGO) and performance-prove goal orientation (PPGO)

predicted entrepreneurial career anchors when coupled with high self-efficacy. For managerial goals, self-efficacy did not influence these relationships. Findings suggested providing opportunities for increased self-efficacy and adaptive goal orientations may affect entrepreneurial development.

Need of the study

It is also widely accepted that entrepreneurship can be learnt and a positive relationship can be found between higher education levels and high levels of entrepreneurial activity (GEM, 2006). There is need to find out the influential variables that enhance entrepreneurial traits among students. These influential variables may in the form of models, approaches, strategies, case studies, organizational cultures, public policies, educational policies, best practices etc. (Culbertson, Smith, & Leiva, May 2011), had rightly identified that influence of goal orientation and self-efficacy in predicting entrepreneurial and managerial career anchors development. However, some researchers argue that graduates' needs for entrepreneurship education do not match actual outcomes in terms of entrepreneurial skills, knowledge and attitudes (Matlay, 2008). On the other side, (Matlay, 2008) author stated based on his research, that most graduate entrepreneurs seemed to be satisfied with the outcomes of their entrepreneurship education, both in relative and in absolute terms. Likewise Academicians, policy makers, policy implementers, professors, researchers need to reflect on their own practices and need to upgrade their own strategies so that they can revamp their curriculum transactions with an aim to empower students in many directions not only focussing on entrepreneurial traits but all other personality traits that may boost entrepreneurial traits in prospective student teachers.

Statement of Aim: A study of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Qualification, Age, Marital Status and Parents' Occupation

Aims of the study:

1. To study of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their
 - a. Qualification,
 - b. Age,
 - c. Marital Status and
 - d. Parents' occupation.
2. To compare of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their

- a. Qualification,
 - b. Age,
 - c. Marital Status and
 - d. Parents' occupation.
3. To determine the factors that strengthens the Entrepreneurship among student teachers.

Objectives of the study:

1. To study of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Qualification, Age, Marital Status and Parents' occupation.
2. To compare Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Qualification in terms of ...
 - a. Graduate and
 - b. Undergraduate.
3. To compare Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their age in terms of ...
 - a. Up to 22 years
 - b. Above 22 years
4. To compare Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their marital in terms of ...
 - a. Unmarried
 - b. Married
5. To compare Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Parents' occupation in terms of ...
 - a. Business
 - b. Service
6. To determine the factors that strengthens the Entrepreneurship among student teachers.

Hypothesis of the study:

1. There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Qualification in terms of ...
 - a. Graduate and
 - b. Undergraduate.
2. There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their age in terms of ...
 - a. Up to 22 years

- b. Above 22 years
- 3. There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their marital in terms of ...
 - a. Unmarried
 - b. Married
- 4. There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Parents' occupation in terms of ...
 - a. Business
 - b. Service

Scope and Limitations of the study

This study covers the perceptions of prospective pre-primary female student teachers studying in Bombay Teachers' Training College Colaba. This study covers the perceptions of student teachers in relation to entrepreneurship traits in terms of Initiative Taking, Risk Taking, Confidence, Passion and Open Mindedness.

Research Design

The researcher has used descriptive survey method for this study. The study was conducted by collecting the data from 54 prospective pre-primary student teachers studying in Bombay Teachers' Training College in the year 2015-2016. The purposive sampling technique was used for collection of data.

Instrument Reliability:

A 5-point Likert scale was prepared with the help of experts. The questionnaire comprised five sections named, Self Confidence, Initiative Taking, open mindedness, passion and Risk taking. There were total 25 items in the questionnaire. There were total 5 items for each component of entrepreneurship traits. After that, a descriptive analysis was used as data analysis approach of the demographic information of the respondents in the first place. Then, Reliability testing was conducted to measure the internal validity and consistency of items used for each construct. The reliability analysis was conducted in order to establish the internal validity and consistency of the items of the constructed tool. The Reliability Analysis was computed and is presented in Table 2.

Reliability

Traits of Entrepreneurship	Items	Chronbach Alpha
Total	25	0.961

Data Analysis

Testing of Hypothesis 1

There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Qualification in terms of ...

- c. Graduate and
- d. Undergraduate.

Table 1 Statistical Analysis - whether level of education determines the entrepreneurship traits

Groups	N	df	Mean	S D	Table value	t value	Level of Significance
Graduate	30	48	80.57	16.17	2.01	2.89	P=0.01
Undergraduate	24		67.50	16.92			P<0.05 Significant at 0.05 level

Table 1 describes the t-test statistics for hypothesis 1. The higher value of the obtained t indicates the significant difference in the mean scores of perceptions of Graduate prospective teacher than undergraduate prospective teachers. These observations clearly support that level of education positively determines the entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is positive relation between level of education and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students. More is the level of education; stronger will be the entrepreneur aspirations.

Testing of Hypothesis 2

There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their age in terms of ...

- a) Up to 22 years
- b) Above 22 years

Table 2 Statistical Analysis - whether age determines the entrepreneurship traits

Groups	N	df	Mean	S D	Table value	t value	Level of Significance
AGE UPTO 22	26	50	72.15	16.62	2.01	0.77	P=0.44 P>0.05
AGE ABOVE 22	28		76	17			Not Significant at 0.05 level

Table 2 describes the t-test statistics for hypothesis 2. The lower value of the obtained t indicates no significant difference in the mean scores of perceptions of prospective teacher having age less than 22 years than prospective teachers with age above 22 years. These observations clearly support that age does not determine entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is no relation between age and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students.

Testing of Hypothesis 3

There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their marital in terms of ...

- a) Unmarried
- b) Married

Table 3 Statistical Analysis - whether marital status determines the entrepreneurship traits

Groups	N	df	Mean	S D	Table value	t value	Level of Significance
Unmarried	38		72.79	18.57			P=0.16
Married	15		79.8	14.91	2.01	1.43	P>0.05 Not Significant at 0.05 level

Table 3 describes the t-test statistics for hypothesis 3. The lower value of the obtained t indicates no significant difference in the mean scores of perceptions of unmarried prospective teacher than married prospective teachers. These observations clearly support that marital status does not determine entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is no relation between marital status and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students.

Testing of Hypothesis 4

There is no significance difference in the mean scores of Entrepreneurship Traits as perceived by Prospective Pre-primary Teachers in relation to their Parents' occupation in terms of ...

- a) Business
- b) Service

Table 4 Statistical Analysis - whether parents' occupation determines the entrepreneurship traits

Groups	N	df	Mean	S D	Table value	t value	Level of Significance
Business	30		77.23	17.39			P=0.25
Service	23	47	71.48	18.01	2.01	1.17	P>0.05 Not Significant at 0.05 level

Table 4 describes the t-test statistics for hypothesis 4. The lower value of the obtained t indicates no significant difference in the mean scores of perceptions prospective teachers (parents' occupation is business) than prospective teachers (parents' occupation is service). These observations clearly support that parents' occupation does not determine entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is no relation between parents' occupation and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students.

Findings of the study

- a) Level of education positively determines the entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is positive relation between level of education and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students. More is the level of education; stronger may be the entrepreneur aspirations.
- b) Age does not determine entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is no relation between age and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students.
- c) Marital status does not determine entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is no relation between marital status and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students.
- d) Parents' occupation does not determine entrepreneurial traits among students. Therefore we can say that there is no relation between parents' occupation and entrepreneurial traits and aspirations of the students.

Discussions on the findings of the study

It is also widely accepted that entrepreneurship can be learnt and a positive relationship can be found between higher education levels and high levels of entrepreneurial activity (GEM, 2006). The outcome of this research also confirms the findings of GEM 2006. (Chaudhary,

2017) in her findings noted that the role of family background and school plays a significant role in predicting entrepreneurial inclination among students. In her concluding remarks the researcher noted that public policy implications for education system in India which largely prepares the students for jobs in public and private sectors rather than entrepreneurship. Whereas (Beránek, 2015) confirmed that entrepreneurship skills are being developed except for a motivation of students to accept a risky business competitive environment. However, the propensity to take risk is one of the basic traits of successful entrepreneurs. Further he concluded that our future effort shall modify our educational content. There is need to emphasis on how to teach students and modify learners' behaviours to accept competitive environment which is risky and mostly unpredictable. The outcome of this research also confirms that level of education has significant impact on entrepreneurial traits of prospective pre-primary teachers, therefore all higher education institutions as well teacher education institutes also shall incorporate some of the modules in their curriculum with an aim to foster the quality of entrepreneurial traits among students. (Pouratashi, 2015), In his concluding remarks he added that education support, personality traits and skill were the three factors that influenced the entrepreneurial intentions of students. (Pouratashi, 2015), suggested that education support has a significant impact on students' intention to start their own businesses, it is essential for agricultural colleges to integrate entrepreneurship education into their educational programs through curriculum development. It is also recommended that agricultural colleges introduce entrepreneurship ideas as a starting point for students to motivate them.

Conclusion

It is also widely accepted that entrepreneurship can be learnt and a positive relationship can be found between higher education levels and high levels of entrepreneurial activity (GEM, 2006). The outcome of this research also confirms that level of education has significant impact on entrepreneurial traits of prospective pre-primary teachers, therefore all higher education institutions as well teacher education institutes also shall incorporate some of the modules in their curriculum with an aim to foster the quality of entrepreneurial traits among students.

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